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The Global Pharmaceutical Sector: numbers and dynamics

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Abstract

Researchers from various fields of scientific knowledge have dedicated efforts to investigate the multiple characteristics of the pharmaceutical sector. Aiming to contribute to this debate and provide material for discussion, this research focused on collecting, interpreting, and making available data and information related to the Pharmaceutical Sector on a global scale. It was found that the sector's annual revenue has almost quadrupled over the last two decades, reaching \$1.48 trillion in 2022. The twenty largest companies have a combined market value of \$3.5 trillion, assets worth \$1.86 trillion, and generated revenue of \$820 billion, resulting in profits of \$181.6 billion. Of an oligopolistic nature, most of the leading companies are concentrated in the USA and Europe, although a group of industries in "pharmerging countries", especially in Asia, has been gaining strength. Pharmaceutical consumption, although still highly concentrated in developed countries, has also been expanding in emerging countries. This trend is driven by nations such as Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS), as well as Mexico, Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey (MIST). Together, these nine countries already account for 48% of the world's population and contribute 31% to the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Keywords: Pharmaceutical Industry. Medicines. Revenues. Regionalization of Consumption. Developing countries.

Introduction

Over the past century, the discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming in 1928 marked the beginning of an era of scientific and technological advancements that revolutionized pharmacology. The pharmaceutical industry, once characterized by the artisanal production of generic medicines of natural origin (Pina et al., 2009), evolved into a diversified manufacturing of modern drugs. Mass production, the adoption of advanced technologies, the implementation of rigorous technical and regulatory standards, internationalization, and substantial investments in research, development, and marketing have become the pillars of this sector on a global scale (Stacciarini, 2023; 2024a; 2024b).

Sociocultural and economic changes, such as accelerated urbanization, industrial expansion, increased per capita income, access to efficient healthcare systems, higher education levels, and an aging population, have contributed to societies' growing dependence on medicines. The increasing integration of pharmaceuticals into daily life and their presence in households around the world have solidified the modern pharmaceutical sector's position in society, strengthening the key players in this scenario: pharmaceutical industries.

In the past, these companies were often small to medium-sized, frequently family-owned, and focused on local or regional markets (ACS, 2005). Today, the pharmaceutical sector is dominated by giant multinational corporations valued in the hundreds of billions of dollars, with a global presence and market participation. With thousands of companies and varying levels of competition, this strategic sector has become one of the largest and most complex in the global economy (Stacciarini, 2023), generating an annual turnover of \$1.48 trillion (Statista, 2023a).

Seeking to contribute to the debate surrounding the pharmaceutical sector, this work is dedicated to compiling, updating, and analyzing diverse relevant information regarding this economic branch. This includes global revenue, the origin of leading companies, their market values, profits, and assets, as well as the landscape of mergers and acquisitions. The oligopolistic nature of the sector, primarily dominated by companies headquartered in the US and Europe, will also be examined, along with the emergence and expansion of pharmaceutical companies in 'pharma-emerging' countries, particularly in Asia and Latin America. The regionalization and concentration of global pharmaceutical consumption will be explored, as well as the growing importance of emerging countries as drivers of growth in this market.

Methodology

To update and discuss the dimensions and complexities of the pharmaceutical sector, a methodology was adopted that included the collection and detailed analysis of global data. Additionally, diverse bibliographic sources were consulted, including articles, books, and systematic reviews, as a theoretical foundation for interpreting and debating the data.

Figures on the sector's revenue growth were extracted from the Statista database (2023a), a German consultancy specializing in compiling and illustrating global information. The economic profile of pharmaceutical industries, covering aspects such as market values, profits, and assets, was outlined from the "World's Largest Public Companies" report (Forbes, 2023).

Information on mergers and acquisitions was obtained through GlobalData (2023), a British consultancy. Additional contributions to understanding the market in Asian contexts were provided by entities such as Daxue Consulting Beijing (DCB, 2022), the India Brand Equity Foundation (IBEF, 2023), and Parexel (2022).

Economic and sectoral reports, such as the "Health at a Glance 2021" from the OECD (2021), "Pharma R&D: annual review 2022" from Pharma Intelligence (Citeline, 2022), and "The Pharmaceutical Industry in Figures" from EFPIA (2022), were crucial for mapping the geographical distribution of pharmaceutical expenditures worldwide. They also provided information on trends in increasing drug consumption and the variations in this consumption across different countries.

The Pharmaceutical Sector on a Global Scale

The pharmaceutical industry is characterized by an extensive product chain that includes everything from traditional and affordable medications - such as antibiotics - that have maintained their essence throughout the 20th century, to highly complex gene therapies and personalized treatments with substantially higher costs.

In recent decades, the pharmaceutical sector has experienced significant and continuous growth, becoming one of the largest in the global economy (EFPIA, 2022). The collection and analysis of data reveal that, over a period of just over twenty years, the sector's global revenues increased by approximately 280%, rising from \$390 billion in 2001 to \$1.48 trillion in 2022, as shown in Figure 1. During the same period, U.S. dollar inflation was 65.3% (USIC, 2024).

Figure 1 - Evolution of global pharmaceutical industry revenues from 2001 to 2022.

Source: Statista (2023a). Elaborated by the author.

Although many companies argue that the nature of pharmaceutical activities involves substantial risks due to the robust investments required for new drug research, several studies (Angell, 2005; Spitz; Wickham, 2012; Prasad; Mailankody, 2017) suggest that this sector is, in fact, highly profitable. Contrary to the "difficulties" narrative often propagated by many companies, information collected from the "World's Largest Public Companies" report, prepared by the American magazine Forbes, reveals that the twenty largest publicly traded pharmaceutical companies worldwide achieved combined revenues of \$820.2 billion and recorded a net profit of \$181.6 billion throughout 2022, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1 - Market value, assets, revenues, and profits of the top 20 global pharmaceutical companies in 2022.

Ranking / Name	Country	Values in billions of dollars (USD)			
		Market Value	Assets	Revenues	Profit
1 Johnson & Johnson	United States	477,4	182,0	94,9	19,83
2 Roche holding	Switzerland	308,1	101,3	68,7	15,24
3 AbbVie	United States	273,8	146,5	56,2	11,46
4 Pfizer	United States	271,8	181,5	81,5	21,98
5 Eli Lilly	United States	265,5	48,8	28,3	5,58
6 Novo Nordisk	Denmark	252,9	29,7	22,4	7,59
7 Merck & Co.	United States	213,8	105,7	50,4	13,05
8 AstraZeneca	United Kingdom	204,6	105,4	38,7	0,09
9 Novartis	Switzerland	200,7	135,9	51,6	24,14
10 Bristol Myers Squibb	United States	161,0	109,3	46,4	6,99
11 Sanofi	France	136,9	136,7	44,6	7,36
12 Amgen	United States	133,6	61,2	26,0	5,89
13 GlaxoSmithKline	United Kingdom	112,1	107,1	46,9	6,03
14 CSL	Australia	94,7	23,4	10,6	2,36
15 Gilead Sciences	United States	78,2	68,0	27,4	6,22
16 Regeneron Pharmaceu.	United States	74,7	25,4	16,1	8,08
17 Bayer	Germany	70,1	144,2	52,1	1,18
18 Vertex Pharmaceuticals	United States	68,8	13,4	7,6	2,34
19 Moderna	United States	56,6	24,9	18,4	12,20
20 Takeda Pharmaceutical	Japan	45,3	110,3	31,6	3,99
Total	-	3.500,5	1.860,7	820,2	181,60

Source: Forbes (2023). Elaborated by the author.

The data illustrate the scale and complexity of the sector, as well as its main players, the pharmaceutical companies - especially the segment leaders. On a global scale, a select group of companies, predominantly based in the United States and Europe, leads the competition. These corporations hold a significant share of the market (Statista, 2022a; Statista, 2023b) and maintain a certain degree of control, even though there are thousands of smaller competitors around the globe. Generally, these companies also achieve higher profitability compared to others. The profits of the companies presented in Table 1, for example, represent, on average, about 22.1% of revenues, whereas, as shown in Table 2, the next twenty-four companies have an average profit margin of 5.9% relative to revenues.

This oligopolistic nature can be attributed to a series of fundamental factors. Firstly, the considerable volume of capital required to invest in research, development, production, and promotion of new pharmaceutical products creates significant barriers to entry for companies with lesser financial capacity (Stacciarini, 2024a; 2024b). Moreover, patents granted to proprietary pharmaceutical companies provide substantial protection against competition for a considerable period, allowing them to set higher prices without the risk of losing market share to competitors (Kesselheim et al., 2017). Another relevant point is that the first

organizations to enter the pharmaceutical sector, at a time when it was not yet highly structured and regulated, benefited from a developing regulatory environment (Malerba; Orsenigo, 2015). This contributed to substantial profits and rapid global growth.

Additionally, the sector is marked by a constant flow of mergers and acquisitions, which results in the continuous increase of capital and influence for many of the major companies. While this consolidates the main players in the market, concentration can have adverse implications for the population, including disproportionate increases in drug prices (Rajkumar, 2020) and even a slowdown in the pace of innovation (Haucap et al., 2019).

In 2022, a total of 784 mergers and acquisitions were recorded in the global pharmaceutical sector, with an aggregate value of \$126 billion, according to data from the British consulting firm GlobalData (2023). Approximately half of this amount was concentrated in the ten largest transactions. Among these, the most notable was the acquisition of Horizon Therapeutics, a company specializing in the development and commercialization of medicines for rare diseases, by Amgen, a U.S. pharmaceutical company ranked 12th among the largest in the world (as indicated in Table 1). The deal reached a value of \$27.8 billion (Sagonowsky et al., 2023).

Reflecting the dynamics of contemporary capitalism, some of these companies are part of vast conglomerates, which are groups of companies operating under the same control center and involved in various sectors of the economy. Thus, although all the organizations listed in Table 1 have pharmaceutical activities as their core business and are classified as such, many of them also operate in related areas. This is exemplified by the American company Johnson & Johnson. Founded in 1886 with a focus on pharmaceutical production, the company now describes itself as "the world's largest and most diversified healthcare company" (J&J, 2023), controlling over 200 subsidiaries engaged in a wide range of activities, from medical devices to personal hygiene products.

Although economists tend to avoid comparing a nation's GDP with the market value of companies - since GDP measures a country's total economic output over a year (flow), while market value reflects the market's evaluation of a company (stock) - this comparison can help us gauge the size and power of the pharmaceutical sector and some of its companies. In this context, the cumulative market value of the twenty largest companies - \$3.5 trillion - exceeds the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of nearly all countries in the world, ranking behind only the United States, China, Japan, and Germany (WB, 2023). Similarly, the \$1.86 trillion in assets equals the combined annual GDP (\$1.91 trillion) of all forty-eight countries that make up Sub-Saharan Africa, the region located south of the Sahara Desert.

When analyzing individual companies, Johnson & Johnson, leading the list with a market capitalization of \$477.4 billion, has a market value that exceeds the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 184 nations. Roche Holding, a Swiss company ranked second with a valuation of \$308.1 billion, surpasses economies such as Finland and Portugal. Meanwhile, AbbVie, ranked as the third largest pharmaceutical company in the world, with a market value of \$273.8 billion, exceeds the GDP of countries like New Zealand, Greece, or Hungary (WB, 2023).

The Growth of the Pharmaceutical Sector in Emerging Countries

Despite American and European companies dominating the leadership positions in the global pharmaceutical market, a group of companies from "pharma-emerging" countries, mainly in Asia, has gained prominence on the international stage in recent decades, demonstrating increasing competitiveness (Jakovljevic et al., 2021).

The continuation of the ranking presented in Table 1 is dominated by Asian companies, notably nine Chinese pharmaceutical companies, four Japanese (a fifth had already appeared among the top 20), three from Hong Kong, as well as one pharmaceutical company based in India and another in Israel, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2 - Market value, assets, revenues, and profits of the top global pharmaceutical companies in 2022 (continuation of Table 1).

Ranking / Name		Country	Values in billions of dollars (USD)			
			Market Value	Assets	Revenues	Profit
21	Daiichi Sankyo	Japan	43,9	18,8	9,4	0,86
22	Jiangsu Hengrui Medicine	China	32,3	6,0	4,4	0,96
23	Biogen	Estados Unidos	30,9	23,9	10,4	1,56
24	WuXi Biologics	China	30,2	6,9	1,6	0,53
25	Astellas Pharma	Japan	29,3	20,5	11,8	1,09
26	Sun Pharma Industries	Índia	29,0	9,3	5,1	0,87
27	Zhangzhou Pientzehuang	China	27,5	2,0	1,2	0,38
28	West Pharmaceutical	United States	26,0	3,3	2,8	0,66
29	Chongqing Zhifei Biological	China	25,2	4,7	4,7	1,58
30	UCB	Belgium	22,4	16,2	6,8	1,25
31	Royalty Pharma	United States	18,5	17,5	2,3	0,62
32	Otsuka Holding	Japan	17,9	24,5	13,6	1,14
33	Shionogi	Japan	16,3	9,0	2,7	0,88
34	CSPC Pharmaceutical	Hong Kong	12,5	5,5	4,3	0,87
35	Viartis	United States	12,4	54,8	17,9	-1,27
36	Grifols	Spain	11,9	22,0	5,8	0,22
37	Teva Pharmaceutical	Israel	10,6	47,7	15,9	0,42
38	Shanghai Fosun Pharmace.	China	10,2	14,6	6,0	0,73
39	Sino Biopharmaceutical	Hong Kong	9,6	8,7	3,8	1,54
40	Sinopharm Group	China	6,8	52,6	80,8	1,20
41	Shanghai Pharmaceuticals	China	6,0	25,6	33,4	0,79
42	Jointown Pharmaceutical	China	3,7	13,4	18,8	0,51
43	China Resources Pharmace.	Hong Kong	3,2	31,9	30,5	0,48
44	Hubei Biocause Pharmace.	China	2,4	39,1	6,5	0,05
Total		-	438,7	478,5	300,5	17,92

Source: Forbes (2023). Elaborated by the author.

With nine institutions listed in the table, the Chinese pharmaceutical industry has experienced significant expansion over the past decades (Yu, 2019; Xu et al., 2020). This growth can be attributed to government support and substantial investments in areas such as infrastructure, raw materials, technology, and research and development (R&D) (DCB, 2022). The expansion occurred in parallel with the remarkable economic growth of the Asian nation. According to information from the World Bank (WB, 2023), presented in nominal value (U.S. dollars), the Chinese economy grew fortyfold between 1990 and 2020, in stark contrast to the U.S. economy, which expanded 3.5 times during the same period. This growth allowed China to rise from tenth to second place in the ranking of the world's largest economies, trailing only the United States.

The performance of the pharmaceutical sector in China is also driven by strong domestic demand. The country is home to a population of 1.46 billion individuals, who visit over one million healthcare facilities, including 36,600 hospitals (Huld, 2023). For comparison, the Chinese population exceeds the total number of inhabitants in all countries of the American continent and the European Union combined (WB, 2023).

As a result of this growth, China is now home to approximately 5,000 pharmaceutical industries (Statista, 2022b). While many of them still focus on producing affordable generic drugs, regulatory advancements, management improvements, and substantial investments in technology and R&D over the past decades have enabled some Chinese pharmaceutical companies to expand their portfolios in terms of scope and quality, gaining international recognition (DCB, 2022). This includes investments in the creation of innovative and high-value-added medicines.

This shift is notable when observing the substantial increase in the number of new drugs in the research and development (R&D) phase in the country, which rose from 95 in 2007 to 3,111 in 2021 (Parexel, 2022). Additionally, China has already become the largest global producer of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs) - substances essential for therapeutic effects and fundamental in drug manufacturing (Nishino et al., 2022).

Despite having only one pharmaceutical company on the list of the most valuable globally (Tables 1 and 2), India is also recognized for having a robust pharmaceutical sector. The country is home to more than 3,000 companies and around 10,500 production units (IBEF, 2023), offering a vast range of generic drug brands. With over 60,000 brands covering more than sixty therapeutic categories (Invest India, 2020), India stands out as the third-largest producer of medicines worldwide in terms of volume - although it ranks 14th in terms of market value. These figures highlight India's critical role as the leading supplier of low-cost generic drugs on a large scale (IBEF, 2023), particularly for low-income nations, earning it the nickname "pharmacy of the world."

In addition to the growth of domestic industries (Dorocki, 2014), many emerging nations have stood out as favorable locations for the outsourcing of the pharmaceutical industry (Mohiuddin et al., 2017). This scenario arises mainly due to the increasing costs associated with pharmaceutical production, research, and development in developed countries. Some developing nations - such as China, India, and Brazil, among others - offer a range of advantages, including low-cost labor, significant growth in the qualified workforce, promising consumer markets, and governments that have been striving to (re)structure policies and regulations favorable to multinational pharmaceutical companies (Kamiike, 2019). These efforts include implementing tax incentives and new legislation aimed at protecting intellectual property.

Regionalization of Expenditures in the Global Pharmaceutical Market

In recent decades, the world has witnessed continuous growth in the consumption of pharmaceutical products (IMS, 2015; IQVIA, 2023). Data from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) indicate that, between 2000 and 2019, the use of antihypertensive drugs in member countries increased by 65%, the use of antidiabetics doubled, and the consumption of antidepressants saw an even more significant increase (OECD, 2021).

Although access to medications has expanded globally, it is still undeniably broader in developed countries. Among OECD members, for instance, per capita spending on pharmaceutical products reaches high levels in advanced economies, such as \$1,376 in the United States, \$935 in Germany, and \$811 in Canada, while in developing nations, it registers much lower levels, as seen in Mexico and Russia, which totaled \$247 and \$303, respectively (OECD, 2021). Notably, despite geographical proximity, a U.S. citizen's spending on medications is 5.57 times greater than that of their neighboring counterpart in Mexico.

A country's wealth is a decisive factor in access to medicines, whether through the direct purchasing power of its citizens or through the support of financing and public policies. Generally, a higher GDP per capita is linked to greater longevity, which can result in a higher prevalence of chronic diseases and, consequently, an increase in the demand for pharmaceuticals. Moreover,

communities with greater purchasing power often have access to innovative and expensive treatments, which remain out of reach in many parts of the world.

Examining the data collected by the "European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations" (EFPIA), as illustrated in Figure 2, we observe that the United States and Canada together account for nearly half (49.1%) of the global pharmaceutical market, with Europe in second place, representing 23.3%. Japan ranks fourth with 6.1%. Among developing countries, China stands out, holding 9.4% of the global pharmaceutical market. However, it is important to note that China's population, totaling 1.46 billion people, exceeds by 300 million the combined populations of the United States, Canada, Europe, and Japan (WB, 2023).

Figure 2 - Regionalization and concentration of expenditures in the global pharmaceutical market (2021).

Source: EFPIA (2022). Elaborated by the author.

Although developed countries concentrate the majority of global spending on medications, demand in emerging markets, particularly in Asia and Latin America, is gaining increasing importance (Jakovljevic et al., 2022). This growth is driven by nations such as Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa (BRICS), as well as Mexico, Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey (MIST). With their large populations and economic growth, these countries represent a considerable opportunity for the expansion of sales by established pharmaceutical companies and the emergence of new local or regional companies. An analysis of World Bank data reveals that these nine emerging countries already comprise 48% of the world's population and are responsible for 31% of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (WB, 2023) in nominal value (U.S. dollars).

In recent decades, these nations have undergone notable social, economic, and cultural transformations, including advances in urbanization, income, and education. These changes have driven an increased focus on health and a rise in the use of prescription medications (Tannoury; Attieh, 2017). Additionally, population aging and lifestyle changes have increased the prevalence of chronic diseases (Nugent, 2008; Nabel et al., 2009), such as cardiovascular, respiratory, and metabolic conditions, leading to a rise in medication consumption.

Conclusions

This study aimed to support interdisciplinary efforts exploring the pharmaceutical sector by dedicating itself to researching, collecting, interpreting, and making data on pharmaceutical activities available on a global scale. It was identified that the sector has experienced substantial growth in recent decades. In 2022, the sector moved \$1.48 trillion, representing nearly four times the value of twenty years ago (during which the inflation of the U.S. dollar increased by 65.3%).

The analysis of economic and industry reports revealed that the twenty leading global pharmaceutical industries hold a combined market value of \$3.5 trillion, with assets totaling \$1.86 trillion. These companies generated revenues of \$820 billion and profits of \$181.6 billion. Additionally, the sector demonstrated intense dynamics, with 784 mergers and acquisitions transactions totaling \$126 billion in 2022.

Reinforcing its magnitude, complexity, and impact, the combined market value of \$3.5 trillion held by the twenty leading companies surpasses the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of nearly all countries, except the United States, China, Japan, and Germany. Similarly, the total assets of \$1.86 trillion of these companies are comparable to the combined GDP (\$1.91 trillion) of the forty-eight Sub-Saharan African countries. As a specific example, Johnson & Johnson, at the top of the list with a market capitalization of \$477.4 billion, has a market value that exceeds the GDP of 184 countries.

Oligopolistic in nature, a significant portion of the leading companies is concentrated in the U.S. and Europe. However, a group of companies in "pharma-emerging" countries, especially in Asia, has been gaining strength. The Chinese pharmaceutical sector stands out, having undergone significant expansion over the past decades and now comprising approximately 5,000 companies and around 3,100 new drugs in the research and development (R&D) phase. Additionally, China has become the world's leading producer of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs).

With 3,000 companies and around 10,500 production units, India also stands out as an important player in both the Asian and global pharmaceutical sectors. Specializing in the large-scale production of low-cost generic drugs, the country produces more than 60,000 brands covering over sixty therapeutic categories. Emerging nations, such as China, India, and Brazil, which offer advantages like lower-cost labor, substantial growth in the qualified workforce, promising consumer markets, and governments committed to (re)structuring policies and regulations favorable to multinational pharmaceutical companies, also emerge as favorable territories for outsourcing within the sector.

It was also shown that global pharmaceutical spending is primarily concentrated in developed nations, particularly in the United States and Canada (49.1%), Europe (23.3%), and Japan (6.1%), with China as an exception, accounting for 9.4% of global consumption. Among the member countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), there is a significant discrepancy in per capita spending on medications: a U.S. citizen spends an average of \$1,376, which is about five times the average spending of a Mexican, at \$247.

However, the pharmaceutical market's interest has also extended to emerging countries. This trend is mainly driven by the BRICS nations - Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa - and the MIST group, which includes Mexico, Indonesia, South Korea, and Turkey. These countries have undergone significant social, economic, and cultural transformations, such as increased urbanization, income, and education levels. Together, these emerging nations comprise 48% of the world's population and contribute 31% of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP), highlighting their growing role as the new frontier for expanding consumption in the international pharmaceutical market.

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